

CONNECT WITH US

WHO WE ARE

The Geneva Learning Foundation (TGLF) is a non-profit implementing its [vision](#) to catalyze transformation through large scale peer and mentoring networks led by [frontline actors](#) facing critical threats to our societies.

WHAT WE DO

Our small, remote team already supports tens of thousands of local practitioners in Asia, Africa, and the Americas.

We focus on scaffolding local practitioners who directly engage and learn best-fit practices and tactics from each other.

During the first two years of the COVID-19 pandemic, we nurtured the world's largest and fastest-growing [digital health network](#), platform, and community, connecting:

The people we support work on the frontlines: 21% face armed conflict; 25% work with refugees or internally-displaced populations; 62% work in remote rural areas; 47% with the urban poor; 36% support the needs of nomadic/migrant populations.

CHALLENGES WE TACKLE

Our largest peer learning community, network, and platform is in primary health care (PHC), with a strong focus on supporting [Immunization Agenda 2030](#) (IA2030), the world's strategy to save 50 million lives from vaccine-preventable diseases.

- **But our approach can be applied to tackle any complex, global problem that affects local communities.**
- Other programmes focus on cross-cutting topics like intersectional **diversity and inclusion**, **remote partnerships**, or **facilitation and leadership** – and span a range of thematic areas from computer science education to health, humanitarian response, and development.

93 active country networks: TGLF's largest country network reaches over 10,000 practitioners at all levels of the health system and across all areas, including fragile contexts

Afghanistan	Burundi	People's Republic of	Gambia	Kenya	Mozambique	Republic of the Congo	Sudan
Algeria	Cameroon	Korea	Georgia	Laos	Myanmar	Romania	Syrian Arab Republic
Angola	Central African Republic	Democratic Republic of the Congo	Ghana	Lebanon	Namibia	Rwanda	Tajikistan
Argentina	Chad	Djibouti	Guinea	Lesotho	Nepal	San Marino	Thailand
Armenia	Chile	East Timor	Guinea-Bissau	Liberia	Niger	Saudi Arabia	Togo
Bahrain	China	Egypt	Guyana	Madagascar	Nigeria	Senegal	Tunisia
Bangladesh	Colombia	Equatorial Guinea	Haiti	India	Oman	Sierra Leone	Uganda
Barbados	Comoros	Eritrea	Indonesia	Indonesia	Pakistan	Slovenia	United Republic of
Benin	Congo	Islamic Republic of	Iraq	Malawi	Papua New Guinea	Somalia	Tanzania
Bhutan	Croatia	Iran	Madagascar	Mali	Paraguay	South Africa	Yemen
Botswana	Cyprus	Ivory Coast	Madagascar	Moldova	Philippines	South Sudan	Zambia
Brazil	Democratic		Morocco	Mongolia	Qatar	Sri Lanka	Zimbabwe

WHAT THEY SAY

"I feel so motivated knowing fully well that I'm not alone. There is now a global support system."
Health worker in the Democratic Republic of the Congo

"I work in rural areas of my country and did not meet any outside experts. I now have evidence to convince any resistant people."
Local immunization staff in Pakistan

"The COVID-19 pandemic is forcing us to work in new ways. The Geneva Learning Foundation is actually setting the pace for how we do things in the future."
Violaine Mitchell, Director of Partnerships at the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)

"The Geneva Learning Foundation's approach is innovative, motivating, empowering. It has the potential to change how we understand and solve global challenges."
Poppy Facer, Senior Policy Officer, Wellcome Trust

HOW WE HELP PEOPLE ON THE FRONTLINES MAKE A DIFFERENCE

- 1 Our approach, rooted in decades of research and experience in learning science, uses **intrinsic motivation** to inspire individuals to link up and collectively lead change within their local systems.
- 2 Motivated people on the ground have a remarkable capacity to identify, create, and implement local solutions grounded in **indigenous experience and expertise** – informed by the best available global knowledge.
- 3 **Connecting to thousands of peers** across boundaries of system levels, hierarchy, and geography multiplies the experience portfolio that each individual can draw on – and **accelerates progress** every step on the road to impact.

The future of development lies in harnessing transformation through hybrid networks fusing digital and physical approaches. Discovering and implementing new ways to support leaders who live and work ‘where the action is’ is essential on the pathway to a more just and equitable world.

TGLF’S THEORY OF CHANGE APPLIED TO IMMUNIZATION

ACCELERATING COVID-19 RECOVERY EFFORTS

In 2020, at least 80 million children under one were at risk of diseases such as diphtheria, measles and polio as COVID-19 disrupted routine vaccination efforts. Over 6,000 TGLF programme participants from 86 countries [created the COVID-19 Peer Hub](#), designing and implementing recovery projects with local resources. Within the first three months, over a third had already successfully implemented these recovery projects, [far faster than colleagues](#) who did not benefit from the shared experience and expertise pooled from such a global network of local actors.

HOW WE WORK WITH GLOBAL, COUNTRY, AND LOCAL PARTNERS

We partner with governments, donors, and global agencies to co-design and implement learning programmes with practitioners and communities in which individuals and teams on the frontlines lead change. Such programmes can be built in three days and scale quickly to connect thousands of learners and leaders working on the frontlines of conflict, poverty, and other inequalities. [For more information about partnering with the Geneva Learning Foundation, contact: \[partnerships@learning.foundation\]\(mailto:partnerships@learning.foundation\)](#)

WHAT ARE THE CAPABILITIES?

Our digital health platform, which tripled in size during the COVID-19 pandemic, covers the [full spectrum of capacity strengthening](#) needs, from knowledge acquisition to implementation and evaluation.

TGLF’s learning-to-impact pathway combines multiple interventions to drive change

SOME OF THE ORGANIZATIONS THAT WE ALREADY WORK WITH

BILL & MELINDA GATES foundation

Bridges to Development

Gavi The Vaccine Alliance

INTERNATIONAL VACCINE ACCESS CENTER

JOHNS HOPKINS BLOOMBERG SCHOOL of PUBLIC HEALTH

THE VACCINE CONFIDENCE PROJECT

unicef

wellcome

World Health Organization